

Influence of HCOO^- on Calcite Growth from First Principles

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Abstract

Organic molecules in aqueous solutions are good candidates in the inhibition of some biogenic crystals growth. The formic acid HCOOH is considered to investigate at atomic level the interaction between the carboxyl functional group -COO^- and the $(10\bar{1}4)$ hydrated surface of calcium carbonate, CaCO_3 , in the form of calcite. Ab initio simulations based on the density functional theory are performed to study the adsorption of undissociated and dehydrogenated HCOOH in presence of water. Relevant adsorption energies obtained for $\text{HCOO}^- + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ on calcite predict that water is essential in the stabilization of the carboxyl group in its deprotonated form. The interfacial properties and the trend of adsorption energies for different coverages are given in details. The dissociation barriers of HCOOH on hydrated calcite are evaluated with the climbing-image nudged elastic band (CI-NEB) method.

Introduction

The interest in calcium carbonate, CaCO_3 - one of the most abundant biominerals on the Earth - is growing in many branches of science, from biomedicine to environmental applications.¹ The formation of calcite, the most stable polymorph of CaCO_3 , is either the main cause of problems in the water treatment process and a mechanism favored to act as a pH neutralizer in water filter systems. The inhibition of calcite growth, in industrial processes, occurs by using chemical additives often severely impacting the environment. Natural organic materials (NOM), are good candidates as growth inhibitors of CaCO_3 as they strongly interact with calcium carbonate in aquatic system. Reddy and Hoch,² using polycarboxylic acids as natural organic molecules, found that the growth rate inhibition effectiveness is strongly influenced by stereochemical orientation and structural rigidity of the polycarboxylic acids. In this specific case, the calcite crystal growth rate inhibition appears to involve blockage of crystal growth sites but still the interfacial properties are unknown. More recently, Reddy³ showed that the growth rate of calcite is reduced by the presence of fulvic acids (FA) and a

combination of FA and magnesium ions. In particular, the author suggested that in the case of the sole presence of FA, the growth inhibition is likely due to binding multiple carboxylate groups at or near the active sites on the calcite surface. Lin et al.⁴ used NOM with different physical/chemical properties to study the inhibition of calcite precipitation in aqueous solution. They show how this process can be described by the Langmuir adsorption theory (i.e. the rate of precipitation is proportional to the available crystal growth sites) and that the driving force of the adsorption reaction of NOM is the entropy change due to the release of water molecules on the calcite surface occurring during the adsorption of hydrophobic macromolecules. In their work, Hoch et al.⁵ investigated the growth inhibition for calcite crystal comparing humic substances taken from different parts of the Florida Everglades. They quantitatively demonstrated that even a low concentration solution can significantly reduce the growth rate of calcite crystal. This fact is attributed to the capability of organic molecules to bind to more than one active growth site. A recent experimental observation⁶ on the calcite growth rate, put in evidence that a Langmuir adsorption isotherm is consistent with the inhibition effect of FA on the calcite crystal-growth rate in terms of a monolayer of active molecules adsorbed on the calcite crystal surface. A large entropy contribution was also estimated in molecular dynamics simulations⁷ performed to study the growth inhibition of calcite in presence of two additives, namely polyacrylic acid (PAA) and polyaspartic acid (p-ASP) both on flat and stepped surface. Aschauer and co-workers⁷ showed that p-ASP will bind in much shorter time scale to the surface and will have longer residence times than PAA leading to a more marked influence on crystal growth. Moreover, the specific conformation of the two additives, despite the fact they contain the same carboxyl functional group, play a role in the different behavior. Raiteri⁸ et al. exploring the influence of organic species in the nucleation of calcium carbonate, namely citrate and aspartate, in the nucleation of calcium carbonate found that, acting with different mechanisms, they both behave as inhibitors. In particular, aspartate acts in the inhibition of nucleation and stabilisation of amorphous forms of CaCO_3 while citrate shows minor inhibition of nucleation. De Leeuw

et al.^{9,10} used atomistic simulation techniques to investigate the adsorption of some organic molecules, including formic acid (HCOOH), in calcite stepped surface. The calculated adsorption energies suggested that carboxylic acids are growth inhibitors due to their strong adsorption. More specifically, HCOOH is one of the molecules with higher adsorption energy on calcite surface.

In general, a large body of reliable experimental and theoretical data on the crystal growth inhibition of calcite is available and yet, the role of chemical additives and their effects on calcite growth is still an open debate. This fact is mostly due to the complex morphology of biominerals and to the different structure of additives in terms of conformation, molecular weight and character of functional groups. In this framework, a theoretical model may contribute to the understanding of the interfacial properties through the description of the electrostatics and the electronic structure of the interacting particles. In the present theoretical work, we investigated from first principles the role played by -COOH functional groups in the surface stabilization process via the sorption of HCOOH on the cleavage surface of calcite, namely the $(10\bar{1}4)$. Since the presence of water is shown¹¹ to be relevant in such processes, different hydration levels were taken into account. We first studied the interaction between the $(10\bar{1}4)$ surface and water molecules at different coverages. The hydrated surface was then exposed firstly to HCOOH by replacing one by one a pre-adsorbed water molecule to reach the total coverage of the surface and secondly to HCOO^- to compare the different behaviors.

Theoretical Method

The present investigation is performed in the framework of the Density Functional Theory (DFT) as implemented in the code QUANTUM ESPRESSO.¹² Ultrasoft pseudopotentials¹³ were used within the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) and, more specifically, with the PBE¹⁴ functional for the exchange and correlation term. The Kohn-Sham equations were solved by using a plane waves basis set and the kinetic energy cutoffs for the electron

wavefunctions and for the augmented electron density were 32 Ry and 256 Ry, respectively. The Brillouin zone sampling was performed with $2 \times 2 \times 1$ k-points mesh. While the GGA exchange and correlation functional gives reliable description of hydrogen-bonded systems, it is also well established not to be accurate enough within systems governed by different types of interactions. In fact, such interactions are strongly environmental dependent. For this purpose, the dispersion corrected DFT (DFT-D2) approach proposed by Grimme¹⁵ and implemented by Barone and co-workers¹⁶ was used to add the van der Waals (vdW) dispersion forces to the interactions between organic molecules on calcite.

The (10 $\bar{1}$ 4)-oriented surface is experimentally shown to be the most stable one in CaCO₃ crystals in the form of calcite. A 3 layers slab containing 12 formula units was used to simulate this non-polar surface and image slabs were separated by 15 Å of vacuum. Thicker slabs up to 4 and 5 layers showed no significant improvement on the convergence of the surface energy that turned out to be within 10^{-4}Jm^{-2} . The entire slab was first allowed to relax until the interatomic forces were $\leq 10^{-3} \text{eV} / \text{Å}$. A more strict relaxation threshold on forces did not lead to a significant change in the final geometry. The bottom layer of the slab was then kept fixed to simulate the bulk crystal and the molecules were placed on the top layer. Theoretical lattice parameters calculated for calcite in the hexagonal representation, $a = 5.0256 \text{ Å}$ and $c = 16.797 \text{ Å}$, agree within 2% with experimental ones,¹⁷ $a_{exp} = 4.9896(2) \text{ Å}$ and $c_{exp} = 17.061(11) \text{ Å}$.

The energy of the surface covered by n molecules was calculated according to:

$$\gamma_{wet} = \frac{U_{s+mol} - [nU_{mol} + U_B]}{A} \quad (1)$$

where U_{s+mol} is the total energy of the relaxed system containing the surface and the adsorbed molecule(s), U_{mol} is the total energy of an isolated molecule, U_B is the total energy of a bulk of calcite containing the same number of atoms of the surface and A is the area of the surface.

The adsorption energy, U_{ad} , was obtained by using the following equation:

$$U_{ad} = \frac{U_{s+mol} - (U_s + nU_{mol})}{n} \quad (2)$$

where U_s is the total energy of the clean surface. The simulation set-up, in terms of size of the supercell, mesh of k-points and kinetic energy cutoff, was kept the same for all the calculations. The adsorption energy per molecule of formic acid on hydrated surface is thus calculated as:

$$U_{ad} = \frac{U_{s+nHCOOH+mH_2O} - (U_s + mU_{H_2O} + nU_{HCOOH})}{n} \quad (3)$$

where $U_{s+nHCOOH+mH_2O}$ is the total energy of the system containing m water molecules and n molecules of formic acid, with $n + m$ representing the total surface coverage. U_{HCOOH} is the total energy of an isolated HCOOH molecule.

An alike expression is needed to calculate the same quantity when carboxylic groups are partially or all in deprotonated form:

$$U_{ad} = \frac{U_{tot} - (U_s + mU_{H_2O} + nU_{HCOOH} + lU_{HCOO^-} + lU_{H^+})}{n} \quad (4)$$

In 4 the *tot* subscript includes: $s + nHCOOH + lHCOO^- + lH^+ + mH_2O$, assuming l protons moved from the acid to the surface. The energies of the formate and hydrogen ions are calculated on the neutral species in gas phase. The bonding charge density was evaluated using the expression:

$$\Delta\rho(\mathbf{r}) = \rho_{s+mol}(\mathbf{r}) - \rho_s(\mathbf{r}) - \rho_{mol}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (5)$$

where $\rho_{s+mol}(\mathbf{r})$, $\rho_s(\mathbf{r})$, and $\rho_{mol}(\mathbf{r})$ are the charge density of the surface+molecules system, the clean surface, and the isolated molecules, respectively.

The mechanism of the dissociative reaction of HCOOH, as $HCOO+H$, was studied by means of the Climbing-Image Nudged Elastic Band (CI-NEB) method.¹⁸ The minimum energy path (MEP) was obtained interpolating a set of nine images including the initial (reactants) and

final (products) configurations.

Results and discussion

Formic acid on Hydrated surface

In order to understand the effects of HCOOH on calcite surface in presence of water a preliminary description of the interaction between water and calcite is given in the following.

Hydration

The clean surface was covered by a monolayer of water molecules. Following the scheme of Reference 19 the coverage is given by the number of water molecules per CaCO_3 formula unit in the surface layer: a coverage of 100% corresponds to four water molecules in a simulation cell in which the surface is represented by 4 formula units. Several initial configurations in which the molecules were differently placed on the relaxed surface were considered and the corresponding hydration and surface energies were calculated both at 25% (single molecule) and 100% coverages. The results obtained for the lowest energy systems are summarized in 1 and compared to other theoretical results. 1 shows that the adsorption energy

Table 1: Adsorption (U_{ad}) and surface (γ_{wet}) energies for different H_2O coverages.

U_{ad} (kJmol ⁻¹)	25%	100%
this work	-98.7	-96.1
DFT-GGA ¹⁹	-87.8	-87.8
ReaxFF ²⁰	-61.5	
Born model ²¹	-81.0	-79.1
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γ_{wet} (Jm ⁻²)		
this work	0.87	0.29
DFT-GGA ¹⁹	0.36	0.09
Born model ²¹	0.51	0.30

is higher for a single molecule than a monolayer but the decreasing of γ_{wet} confirms that a

monolayer of water makes the calcite surface more stable. Our calculations lead to $\sim 10\%$ more negative values of the adsorption energies than other theoretical results DFT-based. The source of such discrepancy can be ascribed mostly to the approach adopted: in the DFT-GGA calculations by Lardge et al.¹⁹ the dispersion correction was not accounted for. DFT-D2 overestimated the hydrogen-bonding, as expected,²² and the adsorption energy resulted enhanced accordingly. Omitting the van der Waals dispersion in the calculations (see Supporting Information for lattice parameters), the adsorption energies in both the single molecule and the monolayer, led to U_{ad} as large as -79.3 and -87.1 kJmol^{-1} that agree within 2% with the results obtained with a similar approach.¹⁹ Taking into account the experimental values for the condensation energy given as -43.4 kJmol^{-1} , we rcorrected the adsorption enthalpies. The results go to the direction of a weaker, but not yet negligible, water adsorption (-55.3 and -52.7 kJmol^{-1} for 25% and 100% respectively). The adsorption free energy of water is reported²³ to be small, -2 to -3 kJ mol^{-1} when water is at the equilibrium distance of 2\AA . This implies that the entropic contribution almost compensate the enthalpy term. The bond distances, as summarized in 2, are in very good agreement with other theoretical results and experimental data where available. Distances between Ca ions and water oxygen

Table 2: Bond distances (\AA) in 25% and 100% hydrated surface. The experimental value 2.43 \AA for $d(\text{Ca-O}_w)$ represents the average distance (2.39-2.64) taken from Table 1 in Reference 24.

		this work	other	exp.
25%	$d(\text{Ca-O}_w)$	2.39	$2.37,$ ²⁰ $2.39,$ ¹⁹ 2.41 ¹⁹	
	$d(\text{H-O}_s)$	1.74	$2.05,$ ²⁰ $1.97,$ ¹⁹ 2.20 ¹⁹	
100%	$d(\text{Ca-O}_w)$	2.39	$2.3,$ ²⁰ $2.35 - 2.61$ ²¹ $2.17,$ ²⁷ $2.31,$ ²⁷ 2.42 ²⁷	$2.43,$ ²⁴ $2.3\pm 0.1,$ ²⁵ 2.50 ± 0.12 ²⁶
	$d(\text{H-O}_s)$	1.74	$1.74 - 1.86$ ²¹	

atoms (O_w) and between H and surface oxygen atoms (O_s) were calculated for a single adsorbed molecule on the surface (25% coverage) and at 100% coverage. The resulting distance $d(\text{Ca-O}_w)$ agrees with experimental data as well as the hydrogen bond, $d(\text{H-O}_s)$.

Regardless of the coverage, in general, all the water molecules line up flat and parallel to the

surface and when more than a H_2O is present, the O-H bonds form the typical zigzag pattern already depicted in other theoretical studies.^{19,28} The water molecules are, in fact, adsorbed onto the surface via the Ca-O_w interaction with a H atom pointing at the closer O_s above the surface to form the hydrogen-bond. The carbonate groups, in the $(10\bar{1}4)$ calcite surface are oriented in such a way that the topmost O_s atoms are arranged in a herringbone pattern within the Ca sublattice, driving this way the orientation of water molecules. The bonding

Figure 1: 100% water coverage on calcite. Left: bonding charge integrated in planes perpendicular to the surface as a function of the distance from the surface; right: bonding charge plotted at the value of ± 0.004 electrons/ \AA^3 . Electron accumulation and depletion are represented by purple and blue areas, respectively.

charge analysis $\Delta\rho(r)$, calculated according the 5, for the 100% water covered surface is illustrated in 1. In the right panel of 1 the bonding charge is negative in the blue areas and positive in the purple ones representing the depletion and the accumulation of the electron charge, respectively. The left panel represents the bonding charge, $\delta\rho(z) = \int dx dy \Delta\rho(\mathbf{r})$, integrated on planes parallel to the surface as a function of the distance z from the surface. The surface plane is set as the origin of the z -axis. The depletion region under the surface

level compensates in part the accumulated charge below the water molecule. The magnitude of charge transfer, as large as 0.10e, from the surface to the water molecules was calculated by integrating $\delta\rho$ at the surface level. The lower and upper limits were z_0 and z_1 (see 1), i.e. the middle distance between the top layer and the second layer (z_0), and the middle distance between the top layer and the molecules (z_1), respectively. The integral between z_1 and z_2 , i.e. the middle distance between the top layer and the molecules, and the vacuum yields to a loss of charge of -0.09e. The displacement of the electron charge will be further discussed in the next section.

No spontaneous dissociation was observed, in agreement with other theoretical calculations, both from classical potentials²⁹ and ab initio models,^{29,30} of water absorption on clean calcite surface. Lardge³⁰ and co-workers performing ab initio molecular dynamics on a (10 $\bar{1}$ 4) surface containing defects such as steps, CO₃²⁻, and Ca²⁺-vacancies, found water dissociation favored at CO₃²⁻ vacancies.

Formic Acid on hydrated CaCO₃

We considered a calcite surface+H₂O+HCOOH system where the acid is in both undissociated and dissociated form. Starting from 100% water coverage, every pre-adsorbed water molecule was replaced, one by one, by a molecule of acid up to 100% coverage of HCOOH. The acid was next deprotonated by moving a H⁺ from the acid to the nearest water molecule. For reasons that will be clear later the number of dissociated ions does not exceed the number of adsorbed water molecules. The entire system, except for the fixed bottom layer, was then allowed to relax and the adsorption energies and bond distances were calculated. The adsorption energy is calculated per acid molecule, according to ???. In 3 are summarized the adsorption energies obtained for undissociated HCOOH and dissociated HCOO⁻. The simultaneous presence of formic acid and formate together with water was also studied. Two possible arrangements of formic+formate were possible, both of inner sphere type: *i*) the acid molecules alternate with water in both *x*- and *y*-directions, in a chessboard-like geome-

Table 3: Adsorption energy for HCOOH and HCOO⁻ on a hydrated surface at different coverages.

U_{ad} (kJmol ⁻¹)	HCOOH	HCOO ⁻
25% acid + 75% H ₂ O	-92.8	-791.3
50% acid + 50% H ₂ O	-97.5	-605.8 (chess) — -597.3 (rows)
75% acid + 25% H ₂ O	-104.4	
100% acid	-110.6	

try (see 2 a,c); *ii*) acid and water are arranged in alternating rows (2 b,d). Henceforth, these two configurations will be referred to as 'chess' and 'rows' configurations, respectively. A single molecule of HCOOH together with water molecules corresponds, in the present setup, to a concentration of 25% of formic acid while the total coverage, 100% of HCOOH, includes four acid molecules per unit cell and no water.

Both in chess and rows geometries the adsorbed molecules of HCOOH are standing on the surface (2a-b) and bridge CaCO₃ through two bonds, one between the carbonyl moiety oxygen and calcium ions (Ca-O_m) and the other one with the hydroxyl-group hydrogen (H_m-O_s) that points either the nearest water molecule or the oxygen of the nearest carbonate group. The latter case is similar to the monodentate configuration found in the adsorption of HCOOH on TiO₂.^{31,32}

The HCOO⁻ group, in the chess configuration (2c), binds to Ca²⁺ via an oxygen atom while the other O forms an H-bond with a water molecule adsorbed on CaCO₃. The H⁺ previously belonging to HCOOH binds the O_s³³ and is further stabilized by a hydrogen bond with the next nearest water molecule, that prevents the acid recombination. Also in the rows configuration the formate group (2d) interacts with the substrate in a similar way. 2d shows how HCOO⁻ can also adopt the stable bidentate bridging configuration between two adjacent Ca²⁺ already observed in the case of dissociated carboxylic acid on TiO₂.³¹ As for the adsorption energy (3), it increases as the concentration of HCOOH goes from 25% to 100% by 18 kJ/mol and it becomes more than six times higher for the adsorption of the deprotonated species. In order to have an estimate of the adsorption of hydrated HCOOH

Figure 2: Adsorption of 50% of HCOOH on calcite in the chess (a) and in the rows (b) arrangements. Details of the adsorption of 50% of HCOO⁻ and 50% of water on calcite in the chess (c) and in the rows (d) configurations. Note the bridge between two Ca²⁺ ions formed by HCOO⁻ in (d). The blue dotted lines represent the H-bonds.

we considered the experimental hydration energy of HCOOH, -47.3kJmol^{-1} . Corrected adsorption enthalpies of HCOOH on calcite for 100% coverage resulted in $U_{ad} = -93.6\text{kJmol}^{-1}$. This value is lower than the original one but still of the order of 90kJmol^{-1} , in agreement with other published results.³⁴ The spontaneous dissociation of HCOOH was never observed in the calculations. Dehydrogenated molecules were obtained, as already mentioned, by placing H⁺ far from HCOO⁻ and close to the adsorbed water molecules to form H₃O⁺. During the relaxation H₃O⁺ dissociated (H₂O + H⁺) and H⁺ adsorbed onto the surface oxygen binding the water molecule through a hydrogen bond. This is the reason why only the results for the adsorption relative to the 25% and 50% concentrations are shown: a water molecule per dissociated H⁺ was needed to ensure the dissociation of formic acid. In all the other cases the recombination HCOO⁻ + H⁺ occurred. We predict that the presence of water and the subsequent formation of H-bonds act to stabilize the dissociated acid accordingly to what observed by Vittadini et al.³¹ in the case of TiO₂. A larger simulation setup is required to be able to describe higher concentrations of formate, similarly to the study of dissociative

adsorption of HCOOH on TiO_{2-x} ³² where the deprotonation was obtained, without water but in presence of oxygen vacancy, with H^+ placed both nearby and far from the molecule. The main question raising is whether the calcite growth inhibiting mechanism takes place via a surface coating (blockage of crystal growth sites) or through a more complex kinetic process in which, for instance, carbonate groups are protonated by the solution and calcium ions bind to the functional group preventing the formation of the layer. The calculated adsorption energies are consistent with both mechanisms but the spirit of this work and the approach adopted is more suited to investigate ground state configurations rather than kinetic effects. Nevertheless, a few considerations can be advanced at this stage. First, in the stable bidentate configuration of the formate a single molecule occupies two surface growth sites which are no longer available for adsorption. Second, the role of water in the stabilization of the ionic functional group on the mineral surface can be further discussed.

To this end, we focus on the configuration containing 50% of acid and 50% of H_2O since

Table 4: Adsorption energy of HCOOH, HCOO^- and water simultaneously present at 50% coverage. chess_1 and chess_2 refer to the two different geometeries where HCOOH and HCOO^- alternate water molecules.

U_{ad} (kJmol^{-1})	HCOOH+ HCOO^-
50% acid + 50% H_2O chess_1	-403.3
50% acid + 50% H_2O chess_2	-373.2
50% acid + 50% H_2O rows	-384.5

Figure 3: Details of the adsorption of 50% of HCOOH + HCOO^- and 50% of water on calcite in the chess_1 (left) and in the chess_2 (right) configurations. Color codes as in 2

it has - in our simulations - the highest concentration of formate. In this concentration, all the possible combinations formic acid-calcite were investigated, including those in which the acid is in part undissociated and in part deprotonated. HCOOH and HCOO^- can either alternate the water molecules in two ways - henceforth chess_1 and chess_2 - on the mineral surface (see 3) or can lie in the same row as already shown in the totally deprotonated form depicted in 2b. The calculated adsorption energies relative to the three possible combinations are summarized in 4 and the relevant bond distances are summarized in Tables S1-S5 (see Supporting Information). The adsorption energies are lower than those of the corresponding totally deprotonated configurations but they are much higher than those relative to the systems where the formic acid is undissociated, thus supporting the fact that the adsorption of HCOO^- is anyhow favored.

In addition we modeled the system in which a single HCOOH is placed on top of a monolayer of relaxed water on calcite. As a result we did not observe any spontaneous dissociation of the acid. Inducing a deprotonation, by placing a hydrogen atom on the closest water molecule (now H_3O^+), the proton spontaneously migrates from H_3O^+ to the surface oxygen (see Figure S1 in Supporting Information). In order to understand the behavior of HCOOH in water, a separate calculation was performed, in which one undissociated HCOOH embedded in a cluster of 32 water molecules was placed in a cubic box of 37\AA side and relaxed with no constraints. A spontaneous dissociation of the acid molecule occurred with the proton migrating toward the water molecule nearest neighbor that in turns dissociates losing a proton that binds to the next nearest neighbor water molecule. No further dissociation mechanisms, but a general rearrangement was the final result. We expect a similar process to occur on top of calcite when HCOOH is embedded in several layers of water.

Our findings are consistent with an experiment³⁵ of heterogeneous uptake and reactivity of HCOOH on calcium carbonate where the adsorption of the acid is observed with and without the presence of water. The authors conclude that under dry conditions the adsorption of HCOOH on calcium carbonate results in the formation of a capping layer of adsorbed

HCOO⁻. They noticed that the uptake coefficient decreases as a function of exposure time until *no more uptake* is observed. In aqueous environment HCOOH can react with calcium carbonate without undergoing surface saturation. In this case ionic mobility is enhanced in the presence of adsorbed water involving also the underlying layers. In order to mimic the above mentioned experimental setup and observe the formation of formate and carbonic acid on calcite under dry conditions, simulations by means of metadynamics³⁶ are needed. The accelerated dynamics, in fact, allows to simulate rare events that occur on such time-scales.

Activation barriers -

The activation energies for the dissociation of the formic acid adsorbed on the calcite surface

Figure 4: Dissociation barrier. Adsorption of 50% HCOOH+HCOO⁻ and 50% H₂O (chess₁) on calcite. For clarity of reading, surrounding molecules do not appear in the image.

were calculated with the CI-NEB method. Both the 25% and 50% concentrations of acid were accounted for. Due to the complexity of mechanisms involved, only the barriers for the dissociation of one proton at a time were evaluated. The initial and final configurations were the relaxed geometries corresponding to [surface + undissociated acid + water]_{initial} and [surface + totally(partially) dissociated acid + water]_{final}, respectively. The results are shown in 5. The dissociation mechanism turned out to be endothermic for all cases. The most dilute

Table 5: 25% and 50% of acid concentrations. Energy barriers relative to the migration of a proton from HCOOH to the calcite surface.

System	Activation Energy (kJmol ⁻¹)
75% water + 25% HCOO ⁻	26.1
50% water + 25% HCOO ⁻ + 25% HCOOH (chess1)	73.3
50% water + 25% HCOO ⁻ + 25% HCOOH (chess2)	465.1
50% water + 25% HCOO ⁻ + 25% HCOOH (rows)	148.6

concentration (25%) of totally dissociated acid was the only single step reaction with the lowest activation energy, 26.1 kJmol⁻¹. The three possible combinations of undissociated and dissociated acid showed multiple step deprotonation mechanisms with a saddle point ranging from 73.3 to 465.1 kJmol⁻¹. 4 shows the detail of the calculated minimum energy path for the dissociation of HCOOH in the chess₁ configuration. This combination results, among the "mixed" ones, the most favored event with an activation barrier of 73.3 kJmol⁻¹. The numbered red dots in the plot (4, left) refer to the configurations 1, 4, 5, and 9 (4, right) representing the crucial steps in the reaction path. More specifically, the configurations 1 and 9 show the initial and final states, where HCOOH is undissociated in step 1 and in part dissociated in step 9. In step 4 of the minimum energy path, between the first minimum and the saddle point, one molecule of HCOOH previously linked to a surface oxygen re-orientes to bind to the water molecule which temporarily links three hydrogen atoms. The water molecule thus chemically binds to the *new* hydrogen atom, in step 5, leaving one proton bound to the surface. Finally, in step 9 the resulting HCOO⁻ is linking the re-oriented water molecule through a H-bond and one proton is still bound to the surface oxygen. In summary, HCOOH gives a proton to the water molecule that in turn releases a proton on the surface. A low energy barrier and a high adsorption energy confirm that the adsorption of the acid as HCOO⁻ is by far favored. In general, the experimental estimate of the deprotonation barrier for HCOOH - as HCOO + H - varies from 21.4 kJmol⁻¹ for solvated acid as obtained from the pK_a = 3.75 value, to 467.5 kJmol⁻¹ as measured³⁷ from photodissociation dynamics of HCOOH molecules (in dry conditions). To the best of our knowledge there is no estimate in

literature of the dehydrogenation barrier of HCOOH on calcite to refer to. Conversely, there are several studies of such phenomenon on metal-oxide surfaces where such barrier is about 128 kJmol^{-1} in α -alumina³⁸ and 73 kJmol^{-1} in titania.³² In both cases water was taken into account.

Bonding charge analysis -

The bonding charge analysis of the calcite surfaces with adsorbed formic acid was performed for all the configurations. The results are illustrated in the right panel of 5 (chess₁) and Figures S2-S5 (Supporting Information). According to the same color code used in 1, the bonding charge $\Delta\rho(r)$ is negative in the blue areas and positive in the purple ones, representing the depletion and the accumulation of the electron charge, respectively. The integrated bonding charge, $\delta\rho(z)$, is shown in the left panels of the same Figures. In addition, the magnitude of charge transfer was obtained by integrating $\delta\rho(z)$ at the calcite surface level and at the molecules level. In the former case lower and upper limits were z_0 and z_1 (see 1). In the latter case the integral was calculated between z_1 and z_2 . The results are reported in two columns in 6, namely surface charge depletion and molecules charge accumulation. Notice, the integral along the entire z -axis is zero.

In general, the adsorbed water and acid molecules do not assume the same ordered alternate disposition as in total water coverage. Their minimum energy conformation strongly depends on the formation of H bonds between the mineral and the molecules and among the molecules themselves. Comparing the integrated bonding charge of 1 (total water coverage) to that calculated for acid and water (5 and Figures S1-S4), i.e. with increasing concentration of formic acid, two effects must be highlighted: *i*) both the blue and purple peaks shift to higher values of z ; *ii*) the intensity of peaks increases with respect to total water coverage. A possible interpretation of such shift is as follows. When the coverage is 100% water, the adsorbed molecules are close (2.39 \AA) to the surface of calcite and we observe a charge transfer from the mineral to the O_w as large as $0.10e$. When we gradually replace water with formic acid, Ca- O_w bond distances stretch up to 2.59\AA (Tables S1-S5 in Supporting

Information). In particular, when the acid is deprotonated, HCOO^- and water molecules form H-bonds not only with calcite, but also with other formate ions improving the stability of the entire system. A similar behavior of a complex network of hydrogen bonds is observed for $\text{CaCO}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$.³⁹

Moreover, as suggested by the higher peak intensity, the charge transferred from the surface to the molecules increases with the concentration of formic acid, as reported in 6. This effect is enhanced when the acid is deprotonated. In fact, H^+ is bonded to the mineral surface which becomes positively charged. Experimental hints of the presence of protons on the surface of calcite under vacuum conditions have been suggested by Stipp et al.^{33,40} As for the surface in solution, measurements⁴⁰⁻⁴³ demonstrate that the potential-determining ions on the surface of calcite are Ca^{2+} and CO_3^{2-} . It results that pH indirectly affects the potential by changing the concentration of the calcium and carbonate ions, as shown by Stipp et al.⁴⁰ and Eriksson et al.⁴⁴

In the present work, the largest charge transfer from the surface to the molecules, $\sim 0.4e$, is observed when the acid is totally deprotonated, i.e. two H^+ are linked to two O_s . As a consequence, such charge depletion creates an excess of positive charge at the surface that would prevent any positive ions, likely Ca^{2+} belonging to an hypothetical solution, from joining the mineral surface. When the coverage of deprotonated molecules decreases, the above mentioned effect is still observable: a sheet of positive charge above the surface and under a negative layer formed by the backbones of the adsorbed molecules. In any case, whatever the concentration of water, the energetics still favors the presence of undissociated acid. Such scenario is likely to be a part of the mechanism by which HCOOH inhibits the growth of calcite on the $(10\bar{1}4)$ plane. This fact is in very good agreement with the interpretation of an experimental observation⁴ of calcite precipitation in solutions containing three different kinds of natural organic material (NOM) which differ for the number of carboxyl groups. According to Lin and co-workers,⁴ the surface charge of calcite as a function of pH results to be positive at pH in the range 7-8 and negative at higher pH. This fact may be

Figure 5: Chess₁ configuration (2c). Left: bonding charge integrated in planes perpendicular to the surface as a function of the distance from the surface; right: detail of the bonding charge plotted at the value of 0.0063 electrons/Å³. Color codes as in 1.

due to an excess of Ca²⁺ at the surface in the first range and to an excess of CO₃²⁻ for pH > 8. Notice, the experiment focuses a lengthscale that includes both the surface layer *and* the molecules adjacent to the surface. Our theoretical model, that allows a distinction of the two contributions, predicts a positive charge at the surface without accounting for an explicit dependence on pH. The excess of Ca²⁺ in the solutions would favor the formation of NOM-Ca⁺ that affects the adsorption behavior of NOM onto the active sites of the calcite surface and becomes the most likely mechanism leading to the inhibition of calcite precipitation. In addition, the estimate⁴ of the enthalpy change of the reaction is typical of a chemisorption mechanism, in agreement with this work. Furthermore, the entropy change⁴ is claimed to be the driving force of the adsorption, possibly, through the dehydration process needed to allow the binding of the NOM molecules to the surface.

Previous theoretical models^{45,46} interestingly relate the charge transfer to the acid dissociation constant, pK_a. A study⁴⁵ of the interaction between water and calcite shows that

Table 6: Charge depletion and accumulation from the integration of the bonding charge (see text for explanation) on the calcite surface covered by H₂O and both dissociated and undissociated HCOOH. Values are expressed in fraction of electron, e.

	ch. depletion@surface	ch. accumulation@molecules
100% water	-0.08	0.06
25% HCOOH + 75% water	-0.08	0.04
50% HCOOH + 50% water (rows)	-0.09	0.07
50% HCOOH + 50% water (chess)	-0.11	0.07
75% HCOOH + 25% water	-0.17	0.11
100% HCOOH	-0.18	0.13
50% HCOO ⁻ (chess)	-0.39	0.42
50% HCOO ⁻ (rows)	-0.41	0.38
50% HCOO ⁻ HCOOH + 50% water (chess ₁)	-0.23	0.22
50% HCOO ⁻ HCOOH + 50% water (chess ₂)	-0.23	0.21
50% HCOO ⁻ HCOOH + 50% water (rows)	-0.25	0.22

pK_a decreases linearly with the Löwdin charge. In particular, an increase of 0.02e on water hydrogen corresponds to a decrease of ~ 3 units in pK_a that reflects, in turn, a relevant increase of the degree of water dissociation. The analysis of charge population, calculated in this work according to the Löwdin method, is reported in Supporting Information. Such analysis depends on the different adsorption of acid that can be either undissociated or a combination of partially/totally dissociated. In the first instance, when the acid is totally undissociated, most of the charge transfer from the surface to the solution comes from Ca²⁺ even though an accumulation of charge of less entity occurs on O_s. In case of partially/totally dissociated acid, the charge depletion occurring at the surface is mainly due to a loss of 0.2e by O_s linked to the H⁺ forming HCO₃⁻. Also, the charge of the migrated proton and that of the C of HCO₃⁻ diminishes. Conversely, an accumulation of 0.02e and 0.06e is found on H_w and O_w, respectively. The same applies to the atoms of the carboxylate group not involved in H bonds. As previously mentioned, the charge transfer from the surface to the HCOO⁻ is higher when all acid molecules are deprotonated. In fact if we compare the Löwdin charges of this system to that in which all the acid is undissociated, we still observe a charge transfer from the surface to the molecules as seen above, but values are smaller by more than 1e.

3 shows that the adsorption energy of HCOOH increases with the corresponding decreasing number of water molecules. Conversely, the same quantity, which is from 6 to 8 times higher for HCOO⁻, has the opposite trend. The different behavior of the two forms of formic acid can be explained invoking the key role played by H-bonds in the stabilization of the two species. HCOOH can interact with the substrate by forming H-bonds whereas HCOO⁻ and H⁺ need the essential mediation of water that makes the dissociated fragments more stable on the surface. The network of H-bonds among formate ions, water molecules and the surface of calcite makes the adsorption of HCOO⁻ very strong. We propose that the coexistence of adsorbed water molecules and carboxyl groups onto the calcite surface is more effective in the inhibition process and, in the specific case of formic acid in hydrated surface, it occurs via the dissociation of formic acid and the formation of a network of H-bonds involving HCOO⁻, water and the surface of the mineral.

Conclusions

We studied, from first principles, the adsorption of formic acid on the (10 $\bar{1}$ 4) hydrated surface of calcite. The two forms - undissociated and deprotonated - of HCOOH were taken into account. No spontaneous dissociation of HCOOH was observed at this level of theory. The proton displaced from the acid to the next nearest H₂O did not recombine and yielded to bicarbonate and HCOO⁻ groups. Conversely, the recombination occurred in absence of water. The proton on the surface and HCOO⁻ are stabilized by the complex network of hydrogen bonds. The comparison between the behaviors of HCOOH and HCOO⁻ in terms of adsorption energies, bond distances and activation barriers led to the following picture: *i*) the deprotonation of the acid occurs via a cooperative mechanism that involves HCOOH, water and calcite. The lowest activation energy turned out to correspond to the totally dissociated acid. A combination of HCOOH+HCOO⁻ and water gave higher barriers varying with the adsorption geometry; *ii*) adsorption of formate is by far the most favored; *iii*) the

bonding charge analysis resulted in a charge transfer from the surface to the molecules consistent with a positively charged surface, experimentally observed. The magnitude of such transfer increases gradually when passing from the total coverage of only water to a layer formed by $\text{HCOO}^- + \text{H}_2\text{O}$. As a consequence the positive charge at the topmost calcite surface acts as a buffer layer that shifts toward the molecules with increasing concentration of acid. Ca^{2+} shows the highest loss of charge when the acid is undissociated, while O_s loses charge more than Ca^{2+} in presence of HCOO^- . The positive buffer layer plays certainly a relevant role in the interaction between surface and solution, but there are other factors including the negative counterpart formed by $\text{HCOOH} + \text{HCOO}^-$ and H_2O , along with their peculiar adsorption configurations (see the bidentate configuration). The combination of the protonation of CO_3^{2-} and the weakening of the surface bonding of Ca^{2+} is suggestive of the formation of acid-calcium compounds that prevent the formation of the layer during the crystal growth and the nucleation of the crystal. Kinetic effects and entropy contributions, as proposed by some experiments, do not contradict the above mentioned issues. Further investigation by means of metadynamics and/or a multiscale approach is desirable in this regard. They allow a reliable modeling of the solvent as well as the calculation of free energies of chemical reactions at finite temperature in simulated systems closer to a realistic model: from a thicker slab covered by more layers of water to a complex faceted structure as a nanoparticle.

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Supporting Information Available

See supporting information for additional details. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org/>.

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Graphical TOC Entry

$\text{HCOO}^- @\text{CaCO}_3$ - Left: bonding charge integrated in planes perpendicular to the surface as a function of the distance from the surface; right: 3D detail of the bonding charge.